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The epic "Manas" and the state of Tabgach: anthroponymic, ethnonymic parallels, analogies

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Resume. The article discusses parallels, analogies, similarities in eponyms, anthroponyms, ethnonyms of Turkic tribal structures (Huns (Huns), Xianbi (Toba dynasty), Se (Si, Jie; Saks), Tutszue dynasty Shabolio (Yshbara), Late Chateau Dynasty (Tang)) in Tabgach State (IV century - the first quarter of the X century) and the epic "Manas". Historical Khitans could be identified with epic Kara Chinese in the epic "Manas".

Keywords: anthroponymic, ethnonyms, epic "Manas", the state of Tabgach, Huns, Xianbi, Toba, Khitan, Kara Chinese.

Эпос «Манас» и государство Табгач: антропонимические, этнонимические параллели, аналогии

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются параллели, аналогии, сходства в эпонимах, антропонимах, этнонимах тюркских родоплеменных структур (сюнну (гунны), сяньби (династия Тоба), сэ (си, цзе; саки), династия туцзюэ Шаболио (Ышбара), Позднетанская династия шато (Тан)) в государстве Табгач (IV в. - первая четверть X в.) и эпосе "Манас". Исторические киданы могли бы идентифицироваться с эпическими кара-китайцами в эпосе «Манас».

Ключевые слова: антропонимы, этнонимы, эпос «Манас», государство Табгач, сюнну, сяньби, Тоба, киданы, кара китайцы.

This is mainly the Huns (Huns), Xianbi (Toba dynasty), Se (Si, Jie; Saks), Tutszue dynasty Shabolio (Yshbara), Late Chateau dynasty (Tang). Chinese historian Ye. Lun-li (XII-XIII centuries): "The geographical environment reliably protected the nomads, and they, uninterruptedly, on the stretch of the century, replacing each other, worried China. At first it was the Huns, then the Uhuans and Xianbians, then the Jojuans and Tutszues, Khitans, Mongols and a number of other, smaller nations" [4, p. 15]. Most modern scholars consider "Jie to be from Central Asia; on the Central China Plain, they found themselves together with the Huns" [3, p. 72]. Sinologist Siratori, referring to information of "Khan's history", makes the conclusion that "the people called "Se"- this is Saka (Saks)" [3, p. 271]. The trouble of eight vans of Northern China and the attraction by them of the northern nomads in their feuds, traditionally called the "five northern tribes": Huns, Jie, Xianbi, Dee, Jiang "awakened in them a taste for power". ... By 316, when Chan'an was taken by the Huns, where the last Jin emperor was hiding, Chinese power on the central plain ceased to exist [3, p. 21-22]. It turns out that the Huns (Huns) finally finish off the Jin empire, and as a result, the leader of the Huns, Liu Yuan, declares himself emperor of Northern China. "In the middle of the fifth century. Syanbians united the North and politically dominated there for almost a century" [3, p. 89]. The Xianbi tribe represented the Turkic dynasty of Toba. For example, some representatives of the dynasty: Toba Gui (386-409), Toba Tao (423-452). They were called tabgachs [3, p. 72].

In Chinese sources there is information where Chabolio-Khan (Nyetu) lived near the Dubin mountains

... his number of troops extended up to 400,000 ... Chabolio ... Khitan was also afraid of the east" [6, p. 215]. Maybe there is a speech here about (Xianbi (Toba)) the same (Shabolio-Khan (Ishbara dynasty, VI century)) in a political subject? Or, as in Iakinf: "Shabolo Hilishi Khan divided their possessions into ten generations or regions. Each chief was given one arrow, from which they were named ten She, and also ten arrows" [2, p. 350]. Chinese She, possibly, this is Turkish Ok (Arrow). According to Ye Lun Li, "Li-Ke-yun fell ill and, being to death, handed over Zhuang-tzu (son of Li Ke-yun, Li Tsung-sui) to the arrow, obliging him to destroy the kidan" [4, p. 350]. So, the arrow was handed over to the Turkic kagan, apparently, from the dynasty of the notorious ten-arrow association On Ok (Ten Arrows People) of the Western Turkic Kaganate. This is probably the first quarter of X c.

M.N. Artamonov: "Judging by the inscriptions on the monuments of Kul-Tegin and Mogilyan-khan in the Orkhon Turks had two main families: Teles and Tardush, from whom the first ruled yabgu, and the second shad. Both of these titles: yabgu and shad are known and according to Chinese sources, where yabgu is transmitted as "she-hu", and shad - "sha" [1, p. 75]. The Chinese shad resembles the name of the late-tan tribe Shato. It is possible that the title yabgu (jabgu, zhabagy) and the ethnonym shato are connected with the name of the military-political subject "on ok" ("ten arrows").

In the epic Manas:

Аскардын уулу Жабагы (Son of Askar Zhabagy)

Ачуусу келе калганы (And began to get angry) [7, p. 256].

Epic name (eponym) Zhabagy could be identified with the Orkhon-Yenisei title "she-hu" (yabgu).

"Kagan Tutszue Shabolyue sent Tutun Panzhi to control the Khitan. The Khitans killed the tutun and fled. In the seventh year of the reign of Da-e (611), ambassadors with tribute arrived from the Khitan" [4, p. 508]. Kagan Tutszue Shabolyue (Turk. Yshbara), most likely a representative of the Western Turkic kagan dynasty (El-bilge-yshbara-yabgu kagan (630-631?), Yshbara Elterish Shir-kagan, 634-639, El-bilge Yshbara-yabgu Kagan, 640-641, Yshbara Kagan, 651-657) and Yenisei Kaganates (Icbara Yamatar) [10, p. 44] in northern China. That means a lot. However, the important thing is that in the VII century. Turkic Khagans ruled over Khitan, took tribute. Before the Khitan era, Tai Chi (Abaoji) was still three centuries old.

In the epic *Manas*:

Жакып: Ошпур деген койчу бар (Zhakup: There is a nomad Oshpur) (7, p. 109)

Чыйырды: Жараткан Жапар кудайым (Chyiyrdy: My God Zhapar) (7, p. 74)

Манас: Атамдан калган жер экен ... (Manas: My father's land ...)

Испара менен Алайды (Ispara and Alai) (8, p. 151)

Алманбет: Жараткан Жапар кудурет (Almanbet: My God Zhapar) (8, p. 292)

The epic heroes Zhakup (father of Manas), Chyiyrdy (mother of Manas), Almanbet (friend, sorcerer of Manas) and Manas himself obviously speak of the same theonym (anthroponym) (Oshpur, Zhapar, Ispara), which could be identified with the anthroponyms of the Kagan Tujue Yshbar (Shabolio), the Western Turkic and Yenisei Kagans Yshbar.

In the period of the 4th – 6th centuries, the population of Northern China was formed mainly of Huns (Huns), Xianbi (Toba), and Jin, and this new ethnos was called the North Chinese "tabgach". In Tabgach, only Syanbi was used, i.e. Toba's Turkic language, and the children were given Syanbi names. For example, Xie Bian, a native of Sichuan, had two grandchildren, the eldest of whom was called Chugub, and the youngest was Chelub; these names were "bestowed" upon them by the Tabgach ruler [3, p. 93].

In the epic *Manas*:

Дөөлөстүн Медер султаны, (Meder sultan Dolos,)

Төбө бийдин Кулжаны (Kulzhan prince Toba)

Төрө Манас баатырды (Manas of the ruler-hero)

Төгөрөктөп турганы (Surrounded by his knights) [8, p. 94]

The epic tells about Toba prince, Kulzhan father, one of Manas's companions. It was possible to identify the Sanbian anthroponym Toba (IV-VI centuries) with the epic name (eponym) Toba (possibly, IX-X centuries). And the name of the genus of the Orkhon Turks, Teles, and the ethnonym Telecians Iakinf, have something in common with the epic name (eponym) Dolos. The Tabgach name of Cheluba strongly reminds the name of one of Manas's comrades Chalybai.

In the epic *Manas*:

Күлдүрдүн уулу Чалыбай (The son of Kuldyur Chalybai) [8, p. 93]

Күлдүр, Камбар, Чалыбай (Kuldur, Kambar, Chalybai)

Бу да келди Таласка, (Profits in Talas,)

Чоро болду Манаска (Became the Knights of Manas) [9, p. 195].

It is known that before the Kulikov battle the historical-legendary heroes Peresvet and Chelubey batyr will fight. It is not excluded that the Mongol-Tatar Chelubey is a companion of epic heroes and characters.

The Byzantine author of the early Middle Ages Theophylact Simokatta (VI-VII c.) writes about the geonyme Tavkast and the Scythians: "Those barbarians who live near Tavkast are a very strong and numerous tribe, and in their size they cannot be compared with any of the other peoples living in the entire universe" [5, p. 160]. In the note: "The name 匈奴 refers to: 1) North China as a whole (cf. Tabgach, Taugach, Tamgach - the usual designation of China in Turkic sources); 2) to the main city of Northern China" [5, p. 211]. The mention of the Asian Tawgasta by a Byzantine writer of history meant the greatness and glory of the North-Chinese Turkic state of that epoch.

Founder of the Liao dynasty Tai-tzu (Abaoji) in 916 becomes emperor ("Tianhuan-Wang - Heavenly Emperor"). The title Tai-tzu was introduced to him in 926 as the founder of the Liao dynasty. To be, the rise of the Khitans begins with the rule of Abaoji (Tai-tzu). Until Tai-tzu about the geopolitical ambitions of the Khitans in Northern China and Central Asia is not mentioned. The political ascent of the Khitan begins at the end of the reign of Xiangtun (860-873), where the prince was Sierra. At which the expansion of the Khitan territory begins. ... When the prince became Abaotsi, to him was subdued five genus of Si tribe, seven genus of *Shivei* tribe and the tribe of *Dadan* ..." [4, p. 30]. According to the epic "Manas", the main enemies of the forty tribal Kyrgyz were Kara Chinese (Black Chinese), i.e. Khitan. Possibly, this historical epoch connected with the epic epoch of the *Manas* trilogy. This period could be localized to the second half of the IX c. and the first half X c. According to the information of the heroic epic, the Kirghiz were divided and scattered from ancient primordial lands in different geographical points of Central Asia, Siberia and China. Apparently, only an adequate regional powerful army could defeat the army of the forty tribal Kyrgyz Zhurt (Kyrgyz Great Power).

Ye Lun-li: "Subsequently, Tai-tzu destroyed the leaders of the seven nomads and again united the nomads into one whole. Then, in the north, Tai Chi was punished by the *Shivei* and *Nüzhen* tribes, in the west he captured the ancient lands of the *Tutszue*, attacked the Si tribe and defeated the latter, after which he again placed the prince over the Xi tribe, establishing Khitan control over his troops" [4, p. 42]. Apparently, "the ancient lands of *Tutszue*" are North China and Central Asia. "It should be said that in the past, when Tai-tzu invaded and attacked the Yunzhou region at the head of an army of three hundred thousand people, Li-Tsun-xu, who bore the title of Jin-wang, made peace with him" [4, p. 42]. Therefore, after the invasion of the army of the Tai-tzu army of the Tang Turks of Jin-wan (Zhuang-tzun) was defeated, and will be forced to go to a separate ceasefire. This could happen in 905. In the epic "Manas" there is information where, after the death of Nogoy Khan (grandfather Manas), a three hundred thousand army of the Kara Chinese people treacherously attacked Kyrgyz Zhurt. It is noteworthy that the historical and epic numbers of Khitan

troops (and the punishment of the Kara Chinese) almost coincide. In the comments: Li-Ke-yun (856-908) was the father of Li Tsun-su - the founder of the Late Tang dynasty, who entered the history under the name of the emperor Zhuang-tzun, came from the Turkic tribe of Shato [4, p. 349].

In the epic Manas:

Naiman, duulat kosho bar ... (There is naiman and duglat ...)

Тарактын Тана бийи бар... (There is a prince Tana Tarak...)

Абактан Айдар каны бар (There is Aidar khan Abak) [8, p. 69].

It is impossible to identify the Late Tang (Zhuang-tzuna) dynasty of the Turkic tribe Shato with the epic name (eponym) Tana, and yabgu (jabgu, zhabagy) with the epic Abak (and Zhabagy). It is noteworthy that the historical Han titles (or ethnonyms) of Yabgu and Shato (as well as the epic Abak and Tana) are closely intertwined.

So, in Northern China from the IV c. to the first fourth X c. could rule the tribe of Turkish origin. This is mainly the Huns (Huns), Xianbi (Toba dynasty), Se (Si, Jie; Saks),

Tutszue dynasty Shabolio (Yshbara), Late Chateau dynasty (Tang). From the above-mentioned tribes and Chinese Jin was formed a powerful state entity Tabgach (Taugach, Tamgach, Tavkast) in the vast territory of Northern China. The country was dominated by ethnocultural traditions and the language of the tribe of Xianbi, Shabolio, Shato. The main thing is that these historical ethnonyms, anthroponymics can be identify with epic analogous names (eponyms). The epic does not speak about ethnonyms (and patronymics, titles), Huns, Xianbi, Se, Shad, Shehu, Shato, Shabolio, etc., although all of them are Chinese written identification (and fixation) of Turkic (Kyrgyz) tribes dynasty. Epic names (ethnonyms, eponyms, toponyms) are primitive and truthful, since the first and subsequent narrators-manaschi artistically sang historical events of that grandiose epoch, where it was impossible to recite it. Apparently, along with the collapse of the historical Kyrgyz Great Power (until the middle of the 10th century) (respectively, of the epic Kyrgyz Zhurt of the era of the Manas trilogy), Tabgach of the "five northern tribes" of China also disintegrated.

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